

ELECTROCHEMISTRY OF FLUORIDE SOLUTIONS. PART I. ELECTROLYSIS OF SILVER FLUORIDE SOLUTIONS

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A systematic study of the electrolysis of silver fluoride solutions has been made.

The decomposition and the cathode and anode discharge potentials have been determined at 29°, using polished platinum electrodes. The decomposition potential curves run parallel to the current-anode potential curves, both showing two breaks, whereas there is no such second break in the current-cathode potential curves.

A black, crystalline deposit begins to form on the platinum anode at the potential where the second break occurs in the decomposition potential curve. This substance has been carefully analysed and its composition found to correspond to the formula AgO_2 , the highest oxide of silver reported thus far.

The silver deposits have also been studied on polished platinum and on silver-plated copper cathodes. Without addition agents, a crystalline but adherent deposit is obtained on platinum, the cathode and anode current efficiencies being nearly 100%.

The addition of ammonium fluoride gives lustrous deposits with a fine, frosted appearance, which can be made use of for some decorative purposes.

Smooth, matt deposits can only be obtained with the aid of certain addition agents, listed below in order of decreasing efficiency:—

(1) Currant essence; (2) boric acid in conjunction with citronella oil; (3) a combination of ammonium fluoride and clove oil.

Boric acid alone, narcotine and brucine do not produce equally beneficial effects.

In no case, however, are the deposits as good as those from cyanide baths.

Shrivastava (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1941, 14A, 535; 1947, 26A, 167) studied a few physico-chemical properties of aqueous fluoride solutions. A systematic study of the electrodeposition of metals from fluoride solutions has now been undertaken by the authors with a view to establishing the possibility or otherwise of using fluorides as baths for obtaining good deposits. This paper deals with the results obtained with silver fluoride solutions.

Gore (quoted by Frary, *Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1913, 23, 64), Mathers and Blue (*ibid.*, 1917, 31, 285) and Sanigar (*ibid.*, 1931, 59, 307) tried the electrodeposition of silver from fluoride baths and found that good deposits, from the plater's point of view, could not be obtained. These studies have been revised in this laboratory and further extended, with the object of gathering more electrochemical data and of studying the nature of the electrodeposits under widely differing conditions. The present work covers (a) current-potential data for the determination of decomposition and discharge potentials, (b) a study of the anodic deposit on a platinum anode and (c) the study of cathodic deposits, with and without addition agents.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Preparation and Analysis of the Electrolyte.—All apparatus, such as beakers, stirring rods, funnels, measuring flasks, pipettes, conical flasks, etc., that were to come in contact with fluoride solutions, were coated with paraffin-wax and calibrated whenever necessary.

Silver fluoride solution was prepared by saturating a known volume of a standard solution of Merck's hydrofluoric acid with freshly precipitated silver carbonate, filtering off the excess of silver carbonate, and making up the filtrate to a definite volume. This preparation was carried out in a dark room. The stock solution thus obtained was preserved in a dark, amber-coloured bottle, lined inside with paraffin-wax.

The estimation of the silver content of the solution presented some difficulty on account of ferric salt indicator not giving the correct end-point, when a silver salt in the presence of fluorides was titrated against ammonium thiocyanate, due to the formation of complexes. After several trials, the following method was ultimately adopted. To a known volume of the silver fluoride solution, sodium carbonate was added till a slight, permanent precipitate had formed; a few drops of dilute acetic acid were added to dissolve the precipitate and then a known excess of standard sodium chloride solution was added; the unreacted sodium chloride was now estimated by back titration against a standard solution of silver nitrate, using potassium chromate as the indicator. The following values show that the error in this method of estimating silver is dependent upon the ratio of the concentration of hydrofluoric acid to that of silver :

No.	Solution composition.	Error.
(a)	10 c.c. of 0.0609M-AgNO ₃ + 0.17 c.c. of 0.3122M-HF	Practically nil.
(b)	Do + 34 c.c. „ „ „	3.4%
(c)	Do + 51 c.c. „ „ „	12%

Since the silver fluoride solutions used in the present investigation did not contain more hydrofluoric acid in proportion to silver than that in mixture (a) above, this method was employed for estimating the silver content of the electrolyte.

The difference between the concentration of hydrofluoric acid used for preparing silver fluoride and that of the silver after saturating with silver carbonate gave the amount of acid remaining unneutralised.

Cell Arrangement.—The electrolytic experiments were conducted mostly in 250 c.c. beakers, coated with paraffin-wax. The electrodes used for the measurement of potentials were two polished platinum foils—cathode being (2.9 × 2.2) sq. cm. and anode (2.7 × 1.85) sq. cm. in area—attached to platinum wires and kept 4 cm. apart. The electrolyte was rapidly stirred by an electrically driven, paraffin-coated, glass stirrer.

Lead accumulators, connected in series with suitable rheostats, served as the source of the current, which was measured either by a microammeter or by milliammeters of different ranges. The voltage applied to the electrolytic cell was gradually increased and, at each stage, the potential difference between the electrodes was measured by the compensation method, using a Leeds and Northrup "modified type" potentiometer. Potential changes of the order of 0.1 millivolt could easily be detected by means of this instrument.

For determining the discharge potentials, a saturated KCl-calomel half-cell of the Leeds and Northrup type was employed as the reference electrode. Two paraffin-coated salt bridges, consisting of saturated potassium nitrate, were used and their tips kept touching the centres of the respective platinum electrodes.

Decomposition and Discharge Potentials

Shrivastava (*loc. cit.*) measured the decomposition and discharge potentials of aqueous silver fluoride solutions at 25°. These experiments have now been repeated at room temperature (29°), particular attention having been paid to reactions occurring at the platinum anode, as Tanatar (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1901, 28, 331) reported the formation of a peroxyfluoride at this electrode.

Typical current-potential curves are shown in Fig. 1. Only a few points have been marked on each curve, but the curves were actually drawn through a large number of points.

FIG. 1

Curves I—II refer respectively to decomp. potential, cathode potential and anode potential. Potentials given are with respect to hydrogen electrode as zero.

The potentials for each of the breaks in the current-voltage curves are given in Table I and correspond to the sum of the dynamic decomposition voltages (Groening and Cady, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 30, 1597) and the IR drop across the electrodes. The potentials corresponding to the breaks, which were not sharp, were determined by producing the straight portions of the curves till they intersected (cf. Shrivastava, *loc. cit.*). The discharge potentials (reckoned with respect to hydrogen as zero) are also given in the same table. For these calculations, the potential of the saturated KCl-calomel electrode at 29° has been taken as +0.2392 volt, referred to that of the hydrogen electrode as zero.

TABLE I

Solution.	Potentials at 29°.		Discharge potentials at 29°. (Hydrogen electrode = 0).		
	1st break (decomp. potential)	2nd break in the same curve.	Cathode potential.	Anode potential.	
				1st break.	2nd break.
2.189M-AgF, } 1.084M-HF }	0.67 volt	0.69 volt	+0.78	1.44	1.47
0.2630M-AgF, } 0.0577M-HF }	0.73	0.79	+0.74	1.47	1.50

The current-voltage curves run almost parallel to the current-anode potential curves, both exhibiting two breaks, each of which varies slightly with concentration. The second break is very close to the first one in the stronger solution and is likely to be missed if the curve is not plotted through a large number of points in this region. The current-cathode potential curves, however, are quite normal.

These results differ from those of Shrivastava in that he obtained only one break instead of the two, recorded above. This is due to the fact that the present set of observations started at much lower currents (just a few microamperes) than those employed by him and the first break occurs only at these low current densities.

Careful observations of the processes taking place on the two electrodes brought out two points. Firstly, when the potential corresponding to the first break in the decomposition potential curve was applied (0.67 volt in the case of 2.189M-AgF solution and 0.73 volt in the case of 0.2630M solution), deposition of silver on the cathode was observed, while no change in the appearance of the anode was visible. Secondly, when the potential corresponding to the second break was applied, a dark green, lustrous crystalline deposit began to appear on the anode. The anode discharge potentials at these two stages were identical with the break-points in the current-

anode potential curves. It is therefore obvious that the two breaks in the decomposition potential curves are in consequence of two different anodic reactions. This point is further proved by two different values for the reverse E.M.F. of the system at the two different points—0.61 volt at the first break and 0.68 volt at the second. With growth in size, the crystals on the anode assumed a deep black, lustrous appearance. The fact that the anode discharge potential became more positive on dilution was noted by Shrivastava. The results given in Table I are in agreement with his statement. He rightly ascribed this peculiar behaviour to the formation of the crystalline anodic product, but he did not analyse the compound completely.

Preparation and Analysis of the Anodic Product

Tanatar (*loc. cit.*) first reported the formation of a black compound on a platinum anode during the electrolysis of silver fluoride solutions. He estimated only the peroxidic oxygen and, on comparing the value with that obtained by him in the case of silver peroxy-nitrate, gave this substance the formula $\text{Ag}_{12}\text{F}_2\text{O}_{14}$. In order to verify this by a complete analysis, the substance was prepared by passing a heavy current (6.8 amp./dm²) through the electrolyte. During the electrolysis, the smell of ozone was very perceptible and the anolyte was found to decolorise potassium permanganate. After stopping the current, the product was scraped off from the anode with a glass rod, washed with water and pressed between folds of filter paper.

Preliminary analysis of the compound revealed that it did not contain any fluorine, but contained only silver and oxygen. The silver content was estimated by dissolving a known weight of it in boiling dilute nitric acid in a platinum crucible, cooling and titrating the solution against an accurately standardised solution of ammonium sulphocyanide, using ferric alum as the indicator. The values from three such experiments are: 76.99%, 77.82%, 76.42% (average = 77.08%).

The theoretical percentages of silver required by different possible oxides are: Ag_2O , 93.1% ; Ag_2O_2 , 87.09% ; Ag_2O_3 , 83.51% ; Ag_2O_4 , 81.82% ; Ag_2O_5 , 77.14% ($\text{Ag} = 108$).

It is evident from the results of the above analysis that the simplest formula for the anodic product is AgO_3 . This is the highest oxide of silver reported thus far. It was found that about 111,500 coulombs were required to deposit the formula weight (139.88 g.) of the compound. The product was next prepared at different current densities from solutions of varying concentrations; but, in every case, the analysis corresponded to the same formula. The compound decomposed on standing, for on keeping the crystals in a closed tube for three weeks, the percentage of silver in them was found to have risen to 79.92%.

The compound, when freshly prepared, has a specific magnetic susceptibility of $+0.37 \times 10^{-6}$; that is, it is paramagnetic, as should be expected in a compound of silver, in which silver has a valency greater than one.

Electrodeposition of Silver

Preliminary experiments confirmed the observation of Sanjyar (*loc. cit.*) that adherent deposits could not be obtained on copper, brass, mercury and nickel cathodes

due to the initial formation of a loose immersion-deposit. Platinum electrodes (2.9 cm. $\times$ 2.2 cm.) were therefore employed as cathodes. Later, silver-plated copper cathodes (this plating being done in cyanide baths) were used for studying the nature of the deposits from solutions, which gave satisfactory deposits on platinum. The anodes employed were pieces of thick plates of pure silver.

The experiments were all performed at room temperature (28° - 31°). The distance between the electrodes in all cases was 4 cm. and the electrolytes were kept well stirred. The deposits were obtained over a duration of at least half an hour. For the measurement of cathode current efficiencies, a silver coulometer was included in the circuit. The efficiency of dissolution of silver, both in hydrofluoric acid as well as in silver fluoride solutions, was also measured and found to be nearly cent per cent.

Table II gives the results of deposition of silver from silver fluoride solutions at different concentrations.

TABLE II

Polished platinum cathodes.

No.	* AgF	* HF.	Cathodic C.D.†	Cathode efficiency.	Applied voltage.	Nature of deposit.
1.	0.2084	0.0161	1.10	95.74%	1.75	Lustrous, crystalline, adherent, poly-faced crystals. Throwing power of solution, poor. Tendency to "tree" at edges. "Trees" peeled off on rubbing.
2.	0.7889	0.1131	2.20	98.85	0.45	Bigger, harder crystals, but quite adherent. Otherwise, same as (1).
3.	"	"	1.05	99.60	0.45	Crystal size diminished slightly. No other change.
4.	"	"	0.40	99.33	0.2	
5.	"	"	2.51	98.05	0.9	Same as in (2). Ageing therefore has no effect.
	(After keeping solution for four months)					
6.	2.189	1.084	1.02		0.45	Harder, finer-grained and slightly more lustrous than that from solution (2). Practically no "trees" at the edges. Throwing power of solution, poor.
7.	"	"	2.12		0.45	Crystals were closer and smaller than (6). Throwing power, better. Slight "tree" formation at the edges.
8.	"	"	4.32		0.95	Throwing power improved further, but long, hard crystals formed at the edges.
9.	"	"	3.20		2.4	Big crystals. "Tree" deposit. No change in throwing power.
10.	"	"	1.02		0.5	Crystal size bigger than in (6), in which the electrolyte was agitated.
	(Without agitation of the electrolyte)					

* (g. mol/lit).
† In amp./dm².

The effect of varying the concentration of "free" hydrofluoric acid on the nature of the deposits was then studied. The results are summarised in Table III.

TABLE III

Addition of hydrofluoric acid.

Polished platinum cathodes.

No.	Soln compn. (g. mol./lit.) AgF. HF.	* Cathodic C D.	Cathode current efficiency.	Applied voltage.	Nature of deposit.
1.	0.2620 0.1416	1.02	97.0%	1.35	The crystals were smaller and closer together than in the experiments given in Table II. Throwing power of the solution improved. Tendency to "treeing" at the edges undiminished.
2.	0.2609 0.2446	„	98.20	1.2	Crystals smaller and more lustrous than in (1). Throwing power also better. Crystals at the edges had a darker colour than the rest of the deposit.
3.	0.2597 0.3672	„	98.53	0.95	Still smaller crystals. Throwing power same as (2). Less "treeing" at the edges. Deposit very adherent, except at the edges.
4.	0.2581 0.5189	„	97.52	1.25	Crystal size smaller than (3). Throwing power better, but not yet satisfactory. Slight "treeing" at edges.
4 (a).	„ „	2.04	97.09	1.65	Crystal size slightly smaller than (4). Throwing power somewhat better. "Treeing" increased.
4 (b).	„ „	4.08	98.55	3.3	Initially, the deposit was adherent, lustrous and finely crystalline. Later it became yellowish and powdery. Loose "trees" at the edges.
4 (c).	„ „	7.14	—	5.1	On "striking" the current, the deposit was smooth and fine-grained; but, on further passage of current it became loose and spongy. "Treeing" at the edges was very heavy.

* (amp./dm²)

Sanigar (*loc. cit.*) found that the addition of sodium fluoride to the electrolyte made the deposits more crystalline, but a diminution of the acidity by the addition of potassium carbonate rendered them somewhat better. It was thought worthwhile to try the effect of addition of ammonium fluoride to solutions containing fairly high concentrations of "free" hydrofluoric acid (as the latter by itself exerts a beneficial effect). The results are described in Table IV.

Mathers and Blue (*loc. cit.*) state that colloid addition agents render the deposits from fluoride solutions slightly smooth. This study was extended by trying the following addition agents:—

TABLE IV

Addition of ammonium fluoride.

Polished platinum cathodes, except when otherwise stated.

Average current density = 1.02 amp./sq. dm.

Solution.

No.	AgF. (Conc. in g. mol./litre.)	HF.	NH ₄ F.	Applied voltage.	Nature of deposit.
1.	0.2569	0.5365	0.0122	1.2	The deposit was slightly finer-grained than that obtained without the addition of ammonium fluoride. It was smooth, adherent and lustrous. The back of the cathode had a rough deposit. Throwing power of the solution improved somewhat by the addition of ammonium fluoride, but "trees" were still formed at the edges. Cathode efficiency = 97.70%.
2.	0.2530	0.5284	0.0554	1.37	Crystal size slightly smaller; otherwise, same as (1).
3.	0.2481	0.5184	0.1075	1.5	Slightly more lustrous and finer-grained than (2). On brushing, it became quite shining.
4.	"	"	0.2468	1.15	Throwing power deteriorated. The top layer of the deposit was grey and less adherent than the lower layer, which was more white and lustrous.
5.	"	"	0.3656	0.9	The deposit was slightly yellowish in colour. The crystals were bigger, rougher and less adherent than (4). "Treeing" at the edges was less than in the previous experiments. Throwing power remained poor.
6.	"	"	0.4414	0.95	Crystal size unaltered. Throwing power improved. "Treeing" at the edges was much less.
7.	"	"	0.5509	0.85	The deposit was finer-grained, smoother and more uniform than in (6). Throwing power also was somewhat better. There was only slight "tree" growth at the edges.
8.	"	"	0.8734	0.75	Same as in (7).
9.	"	"	1.462	0.55	Deposit was more white, finer-grained and more adherent than in (8); but the back of the cathode had bigger and rougher crystals. Throwing power unaltered. There were, however, no "trees" at the edges.
10(a).	"	"	1.986	0.5	Deposit was of the same type as in (9).
10(b).	"	"	"	0.4	Deposition was tried on silver-plated copper cathodes. The deposits were of the same nature as in 10 (a).

(1) Clove oil along with ammonium fluoride; (2) borax, ammonium fluoride and clove oil, together; (3) narcotine; (4) brucine; (5) currant essence; (6) boric acid; (7) boric acid and citronella oil, together.

The results obtained are summarised below.

Clove oil + ammonium fluoride.—A saturated solution of clove oil in water was prepared and the clear, aqueous extract added to the following solution in small quantities at a time: 264 c.c. of 0.2481M-AgF; 0.5184 M-HF; 1.986M-NH₄F. The current density employed was 1.02 amp./dm². The best results were obtained by adding 6 c.c. of the solution. The deposit on the platinum cathode now became matt, smooth and adherent, but less lustrous than before. Under the microscope, it was found to consist of very fine crystals. The throwing power of the solution, however, was poor. On silver-plated copper the deposit was of the same type; it could stand scratch-brushing, but it was not as good a deposit as from a cyanide bath. Further additions of the clove oil extract (up to 11.5 c.c.) increased the size of the crystals, although the throwing power improved slightly. In all these experiments, there was no "treering" at the edges.

Borax + clove oil + ammonium fluoride.—To the same solution (containing 11.5 c.c. of the clove oil extract), gradually increasing amounts of borax were added (0.8-8.4 g.). In all cases loose and non-adherent deposits were obtained.

Narcotine.—Small additions of the alkaloid gave smooth and adherent deposits, but they were not so matt as those obtained by the addition of clove oil. Higher concentrations of narcotine did not prove beneficial. Increase in temperature (55°) improved the whiteness of the deposits, but the crystal size increased. Agitation of the electrolyte at this temperature was found essential to secure uniformity of the deposits.

Brucine.—This addition agent only produced a slight decrease of the grain-size. The maximum effect was obtained at low concentrations (0.02 g./litre). In no case were the results with polished platinum cathode encouraging enough for trying deposition on silver-plated copper.

Currant essence.—A sample of Merck's "Fruit Ether (currant)", incidentally, gave some very good deposits. The results are given in Table V.

The essence (1.8 c.c.) was made up with water to a volume of 33.4 c.c. This solution was then added in increasing amounts to a solution of silver fluoride, acidified with hydrofluoric acid.

Boric acid.—Sanigar (*loc. cit.*) reported good deposits from some fluoborate solutions. The addition of boric acid was therefore tried, but the quantities were very small as compared to those used by him. The size of the crystals and "treering" at the edges were slightly reduced, but beyond that, no other beneficial effects were observed.

Boric acid + citronella oil.—Finally, citronella oil was added to these fluoborate solutions. A saturated solution of the oil was prepared as in the case of clove oil and the aqueous extract added with the following results.

TABLE V

Addition of currant essence.

Original solution = 123 c.c. of 0.2170*M*-AgF; 0.3364*M*-HF. Except when otherwise stated, polished platinum cathodes were used and the current density employed was 1.02 amp./dm².

No.	Total addition of the essence soln.	Applied voltage.	Nature of deposit.
1.	0.25 c.c.	1.25	Lustrous, uniform, smooth and yellow in appearance. Grey-coloured "trees" at the edges. Throwing power of the solution, fairly good. Cathode current efficiency = 94.62%.
2.	1.25	1.5	Smooth, matt, very fine-grained and adherent. It had a white surface, with a bluish tinge. Under the microscope, it appeared wavy and non-crystalline; even at high magnifications, no crystalline structure was apparent, the surface resembling very fine particles closely packed together. There was, however, some "treeing" at the edges. On brushing, the "trees" peeled off, but the rest of the deposit became lustrous. Throwing power of the solution was unaltered. Cathode current efficiency = 96.42%
2(a).	"	—	Passing a current of 4.05 amp./dm ² for a few minutes gave initially a smooth, matt deposit.
2(b).	"	" 4.0	A 25 min. deposit was obtained at a current density of 5.10 amp./dm ² . It was powdery and rougher and darker than that in (2). On rubbing it peeled off. "Treeing" at the edges was heavy.
3.	2.25	2.0	The deposit was slightly bigger-grained than (2), and had a yellowish tinge. Otherwise, it was same as (2). Throwing power of the solution was poor.
3(a).	"	"	Deposit was obtained on silver-plated copper cathode. It was similar to (3). On scratch-brushing, the "trees" gave way, but the rest of the deposit became lustrous and frosted in appearance.
4.	3.25	2.1	Crystal size increased.
5.	5.25	2.0	More white than (4). Crystal size same.
6.	8.25	2.4	Grey patches on the deposit, even after washing with water and alcohol. Otherwise, same as (5).
7.	13.25	2.2	"Treeing" at the edges increased. Deposit had a brownish appearance. All other features remained unaltered.
8.	20.25	2.8	Greenish blue, non-adherent, "treed" deposit.

TABLE VI

Addition of boric acid and citronella oil together.

Unless otherwise mentioned, platinum cathodes were used, C. D. = 1.02 amp./dm². Original soln. = 200 c.c. of 0.2589M-AgF, 0.4570M-HF + 12.0 c.c. of a saturated solution of boric acid at 32°

No.	Total addition of citronella oil extract.	Applied voltage.	Nature of deposit.
1.	2 c.c.	2.0	Smooth and regular, but not very fine-grained. Slight "treeing" at the edges. Throwing power of the solution, poor.
2.	..	1.6	The experiment was repeated after 24 hours. The deposit became somewhat bigger-grained
3.	4	1.1	Deposit was obtained on silver-plated copper. The grain-size and other features were the same as (1). On scratch-brushing, that at the back of the cathode peeled off, but the one on the other side became quite lustrous.
3(a).	..	1.4	The experiment was repeated after 19 hours, using a polished platinum cathode. The deposit was somewhat powdery and non-adherent.
3(b).	..	0.9	The above experiment was tried at a lower current density, viz., 0.51 amp./dm. ² The deposit was now quite fine-grained and adherent.
4.	7	1.45	A matty, smooth, very fine-grained deposit was obtained. Loose "trees" at the edges. Throwing power of the solution, fairly good.
4(a).	..	2.0	Deposit on silver-plated copper was of the same nature as (4). It was better than that from solution (3) and could stand scratch-brushing.
5.	10	1.65	Throwing power of the solution improved further, but the deposit was slightly bigger-grained and crystalline in appearance.
6.	10 c.c. + 0.2 c.c. of the oil itself.	1.65	Yellowish white deposit, consisting of isolated groups of crystals. The platinum cathode was uncovered at several points. Throwing power of the solution deteriorated considerably.

C O N C L U S I O N S

Results given in Tables II and III reveal that although the addition of hydrofluoric acid to silver fluoride solutions improves the deposits slightly, they are not at all fit for plating purposes.

The introduction of high concentrations of ammonium fluoride into the baths produced beneficial effects [experiment 10 (b), Table IV]. The deposits obtained from these solutions on silver-plated copper cathodes were quite adherent, lustrous and hard and free from "trees" at the edges. They could stand scratch-brushing, a treatment which imparted a beautiful frosty appearance to the surface that can be made use of for decorative purposes.

Smooth, matty deposits could only be produced with the aid of certain addition agents. Currant essence was most efficient in this respect [experiments 2, 3 and 3 (a), Table V]. Although these deposits were quite adherent and could be scratch-brushed, they could not take on as high a polish as those from cyanide baths. The deposits obtained by using boric acid along with citronella oil, as well as a combination of ammonium fluoride and clove oil, were also smooth, but these were not as good as those from solutions containing currant essence.

In general, the best deposits obtained in these studies do not come up to the excellence of those from cyanide baths.

The authors are grateful to Dr. S. Ramachandra Rao, Professor of Physics, University of Mysore, for having kindly measured the magnetic susceptibility of the silver dioxide.

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Received March 13, 1951.